

Preliminary Results of Endoscopic Treatment of Vesicoureteral Reflux with Dextranomer/Hyaluronic Acid Copolymer in Children

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Abstract

Background: Endoscopic treatment with various bulking agents has been widely used as a therapy for vesicoureteral reflux (VUR), because it is simpler, less time-consuming, and less painful than traditional surgeries. The ideal bulking agent for the injection therapies must be easily injectable, volume- stable, biocompatible, non-antigenic, non-migratory and with durable results.

Objective: To evaluate the preliminary results of endoscopic treatment of vesicoureteral reflux with dextranomer/hyaluronic acid copolymer in children.

Patients and Methods: Forty three patients with 66 refluxing renal unit (RRU), 23 (53.5%) male and 20(46.5%) female, with a mean age of 4.7 years (range: 4 months to 12 years), were treated endoscopically with Dextranomer/hyaluronic acid copolymer(Dx/HA) injection, in the Urological Department of Al-Sader Medical City/ Al-Najaf Al-Ashraf, and followed for a minimum of 12 months, VUR was unilateral in 20 (46.5%) and bilateral in 23 (53.5%) patients. The

reflux was from grade II to V in: 2 (3%), 20 (30.3%), 26 (39.4%), 18 (27.3%) RRU respectively. The volume of Dx/HA injected was: 0.4 mL- 3mL per RRU with a mean of 1 mL.

Results: All patients completed at least 12 months of follow up, reflux was disappeared in 45 RRU (68.1%) after just one injection, 21 RRU (31.9%) received a second injection, with reflux successfully disappeared in 12 RRU (57.1%) of the 21 RRU, and success rate of total group of RRU was 86.4%. Complications were: Two patients (4.6%) with 2 RRU (3%) develop ureteral obstruction, UTIs in 4 patients (9.3%) in the first 6 months postoperatively.

Conclusions: The success rate shows that endoscopic treatment of VUR is very effective, and it can be considered the first line treatment option for VUR, with a low rate of complications.

Introduction

Vesicoureteral reflux (VUR) is the retrograde flow of urine from the bladder into the upper urinary tract, vesicoureteral reflux is the most common abnormality of the urinary tract in children, affecting 1% of all children [1, 26].

Is estimated to be approximately 30% for children with UTI and 17% without infection [2, 27]. In asymptomatic infants followed up for antenatal hydronephrosis, the prevalence of reflux ranges from 15% in infants with absent or mild hydronephrosis on postnatal ultrasound [3], to 38% in a group of neonates with various postnatal upper tract sonographic anomalies including

More Information

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vesicoureteral reflux (VUR), endoscopic treatment, injection therapy, dextranomer, hyaluronic acid copolymer.

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hydronephrosis, and renal agenesis [4]. Siblings of children with VUR had a 27.4% risk of also having VUR, whereas the offspring of parents with VUR had a higher incidence reaching 35.7% [5].

Urinary tract infections are more common in girls than boys due to anatomical differences, however, among all children with UTIs, boys are more likely to have VUR than girls (29% vs. 14%) [6]. Boys also tend to have higher grades of VUR diagnosed at younger ages, although their VUR is more likely to resolve [6]. Boys appear to harbor postnatal reflux more commonly, a 6:1 male-to-female ratio was reported [3].

Because the natural history of reflux involves spontaneous resolution over time, it is evident that less primary reflux would be prevalent in older children compared with infants. Even in the presence of infection or asymptomatic bacteriuria, reflux is more common in younger patients [8].

In general, reflux is considered primary if the main reason for it, is a fundamental deficiency in the function of the ureterovesical junction (UVJ) antireflux mechanism, while remaining factors (bladder and ureters) remain normal or relatively noncontributory [3]. Secondary reflux, then, implies reflux caused by overwhelming the normal function of the UVJ, bladder dysfunction of a congenital, acquired, or behavioral nature is often the main cause of secondary reflux [9]. In male, the most common anatomic obstruction of the bladder is posterior urethral valves (PUVs) [28]. Reflux is present in 48% to 70% of PUV patients [10]. In females, anatomic bladder obstruction is rare, the most common structural obstruction is from an ureterocele, which prolapses into the bladder neck [11].

Figure 1: Equipments for Endoscopic Injection Treatment: A. The Offset Lens Cystoscope, B, Injection Needle, C, Prefilled Syringe of Dx/HA (Dexell)

Bladder-bowel dysfunction (BBD): Bladder-bowel dysfunction can manifest as any combination of enuresis, constipation, urinary frequency and urgency, dysuria, infrequent voiding or even encopresis [29]. Its presence has been seen to delay and/or decrease the rate of primary VUR resolution, incite secondary VUR

and increase the rate of breakthrough UTIs [5]. Recent studies have documented BBD in more than 40% of patients with VUR [12].

In 1981 the International Reflux Study Committee proposed a system of five grades of reflux that remains in current use today [8], as shown in figure 1.

Patients and Methods

Since February 2013 to December 2014, a total number of 43 children with 66 refluxing renal unit (RRU) were enrolled in this prospective study and endoscopically treated in the Urological Department-Al-Sadder Medical City/ Al- Najaf Al-Ashraf, their ages ranged between 4 months and 12 years (the mean age was 4.7 years), and their data on: sex, reflux grade, laterality and endoscopic treatment results in different grades of reflux, were analysed.

All patients were evaluated by history with having had at least one confirmed UTI with culture and sensitivity, then by U/S to assess: degree of dilatation of ureter and pelvicalyceal system and corticomedullary differentiation of the kidney, and then the diagnosis was confirmed by VCUg after treatment of UTIs 1.

After diagnosis, treatment for UTI was started according to culture and sensitivity, and then a urinary chemoprophylaxis was initiated after resolution of UTI. If endoscopic treatment is decided to the patient a conventional preoperative preparation was done by urinalysis and blood tests.

The radiological grading of VUR was done according to the international system introduced by the International Reflux Study Committee in 1981 [13].

The indications for surgery were breakthrough febrile UTIs while on antibiotics, decline in the renal functions, and parents' preference after explanation of all treatment options.

All procedures were performed with the child in the lithotomy position under general anesthesia, and all patients received parenteral antibiotic prophylaxis immediately prior to the procedure.

Using the offset-lens pediatric cystoscope with a straight working channel (R.Wolf, Germany, 8-9.8 Fr), routine cystoscopy was performed, then the bladder was partially filled by glycine fluid to permit visualization of the ureteric orifices and to avoid tension within the submucosal layer of the ureter secondary to overdistention.

A flexible cystoscopic injection needle (COOK MEDICAL, Williams, Ireland) consisting of a tip needle of 8 mm long, 23 gauge, 3.7 Fr, with a total needle length of 35 cm as shown in figure 2, was used for injection.

We performed STING technique in which the needle is placed submucosally at the 6 o'clock position, approximately 2-3 mm distal to the ureteral orifice and was advanced proximally into the submucosal plane for a distance of 4 to 5 mm, then Dx/HA was injected until

the orifice was elevated and coapted, and a volcano bulge narrowed the ureteral orifice.

In patients with golf-hole ureteral orifices (higher grades reflux), the HIT (Hydrodistension Implantation Technique) or the Double HIT procedure were performed. In HIT procedure the ureter is hydrodistended so that the needle may be placed inside the ureteral tunnel, a few millimeters within the orifice [30].

In Double HIT procedure the first injection of Dx/HA done for few millimeters inside the refluxing ureteral orifice after hydrodistension, the second injection is similar to STING technique but more cephalad.

In most patients, only 1 puncture at 6 o'clock was needed. Only in a few patients, when an adequate subureteral mound was not attained, another puncture was performed at a different location, depending on local findings [31].

All patients were catheterized post injection, and received conventional intraoperative and inward pediatric monitoring, and were discharged on the next day after surgery with catheter removal, while keeping them on urinary prophylaxis until the disappearance of reflux is confirmed by VCUg after 3 months.

An abdominal ultrasound was performed in all cases at four weeks post-operatively and at the sixth and twelfth post-operative months to detect degree of hydronephrosis.

All patients underwent VCUg three months after the treatment, in order to confirm the success of treatment. The second VCUg only performed in patients who develop recurrent febrile UTIs after successful initial treatment.

Patients who failed initial injection were further clinically observed, or they got second injection, usually after six months [31], if there is still no resolution, then ureteral reimplantation surgery is recommended.

No patient was offered more than 2 injections. Successful reflux correction was defined as absent reflux confirmed by normal VCUg after one or two injections.

All patients have been followed for a minimum of 12 months.

Results

Forty three patients were included in this prospective study from February 2013 to December 2014, with a mean age of 4.7 years (range between 4 months and 12 years). Boys comprise 53.5% (23 boys), and girls 46.5% (20 girls), with female to male ratio of 1:1.15 as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Sex Frequency

SEX	No. of patients	%
Female	20	46.5
Male	23	53.5
Total	43	100

Reflux grades from II to V in this study as follows: grade II in 2 ureters (3%), grade III in 20 ureters (30.3%), grade IV in 26 ureters (39.4%), and grade V in 18 ureters (27.3%). Reflux was unilateral in 20 patients (46.5 %) , right side in 10 (23.25%) patients and left side in 10 (23.25%) patients, and bilateral in 23 (53.5%), comprising 66 RRU as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Laterality Frequency

Laterality	No. of RRU			%
Unilateral	Right	10	20	46.5
	Left	10		
bilateral	23			53.5
Total	43			100

All of those have VUR, diagnosed by U/S and confirmed by VCUg and all patients underwent endoscopic treatment with Dx/HA, under GA, with a mean volume of Dx/HA used for injection was 1 mL (range from 0.4 – 3 mL).

Of the total 66 RRU, in 45 RRU (68.2%) reflux was completely disappeared after only one endoscopic injection treatment, and 21 of 66 RRU (31.8%) received a second endoscopic injection treatment, after which the reflux was disappeared successfully in 12 of 21 RRU (57.1%), raising the success rate in the disappearance of VUR after two injections of Dx/HA to (86.4%) of the total group of RRU (57 of 66 RRU) as shown in tables 3.

Table 3: Success Rate in Relation to Injection Number

Injection number	No. of RRU	Success: no. of ureters (%)
1	66	45 (68.1)
2	18	12(57.1)
Total	84	57(86.4)

Success rates were decreasing with increasing grade of VUR as follows: grade II: 100%, grade III: 95%, grade IV: 88, 4%, grade V: 72.2%, as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Success Rate According to the Grade of VUR

grade	No. of RRU	Success: no. of RRU (%)
II	2	2 (100)
III	20	19 (95)
IV	26	23 (88.4)
V	18	13 (72.2)
Total	66	57(86.4)

Nine RRU was without response after two endoscopic injection treatments (5 with VUR grade V, 3 with VUR grade IV, and 1 with VUR grade III) and were planned to do an open ureteral reimplantation surgery for them. Postoperative complications are summarized in table 5.

Table 5: Post-Operative Complications

	COMPLICATION	NO. (%)
1	Ureteral obstruction	2 patients (4.6%) with 2 RRU (3%)
2	Urinary tract infections within the first six months	4 patients (9.3%)
3	Mild transient hydronephrosis	12 patients (28%) with 15 RRU (23%)
4	Treatment failure	9 RRU (13.6 %)

Discussion

Vesicoureteral reflux is a common clinical entity, and many treatment options are exist. The main goal of treatment of VUR is to prevent febrile UTI and preserve renal function [35]. Although spontaneous resolution in primary reflux is common, surgical intervention may be needed in patients with: persistent reflux, breakthrough febrile UTI, or renal scarring [8, 12].

Previously, long-term administration of antibiotics as prophylaxis for UTI has been advocated as the preferred management option for VUR in children [37]. Schwab and colleagues determined the resolution rate of patients with VUR on observation therapy, they found that reflux grades 1–3 resolved at a rate of 13% yearly during the initial 5 years of follow-up and then at a rate of 3.5% yearly during subsequent follow-up, reflux grades 4 and 5 resolved at a rate of 5% yearly, bilateral reflux resolved more slowly than unilateral reflux, and it resolved more rapidly in boys than in girls [19].

The only alternative management of low-dose antibiotic prophylaxis was open surgery. With the advance in surgical endoscopy, cystoscopic injection of bulking agents has gained popularity and became an established alternative to long-term antibiotic prophylaxis and ureteral reimplantation surgery for the treatment of VUR [18].

Endoscopic Dx/ HA injection use has dramatically increased in recent years, with some authors even recommending Dx/HA injection as the optimal first-line VUR treatment [21, 36]. This increased use is generally attributed to the minimally invasive nature and perceived technical simplicity of the procedure [36], with an almost immediate postoperative recovery, with a much lower postoperative complications rate [22].

In this study 43 patients with VUR (66 RRU) underwent endoscopic treatment, and the success was defined as resolution of VUR after first or second injection on postoperative VCUG performed 3 months following endoscopic treatment [31].

The number of patients enrolled in this research showed a cure rate of 68.1 % after one Dx/HA injection

and up to 86.4 % after a second injection [31]. The success rates in our study are close to the success rates reported in different series as shown in table 6 [23].

In a meta-analysis that examined all types of injections (including Dx/HA) in 5527 patients and 8101 RRU, success rates of 78.5% for grades I and II, 72% for grade III, 63% for grade IV, and 51% for grade V reflux were reported [32]. In cases when the first treatment was unsuccessful, the second injection had a success rate of 68% and the third had a success rate of 34% [32]. The success rate was lower for duplicated than for single systems (50% vs. 73%) and lower for neuropathic (62%) than for normal bladders (74%) [24, 32].

Patients treated with Dx/HA injection in our study experienced few complications, as follows:

Ureteral obstruction in 3% of RRU and 4.6% of patients, some studies reported 0.7% of patient with Dx/HA injection developed symptomatic ureteral obstruction and necessitated surgical intervention [33], although ureteral obstruction has been described as a non-frequent and temporary complication [25].

However 18% of the Dx/HA volume is absorbed after a few weeks of the injection, and an additional 1% volume reduction occurs within 3 months, possibly alleviating this temporary obstruction, and it can take weeks to months to a complete resolution of the hydronephrosis[26].

We have 4 patients (9.3%) developed UTI within the first six months post endoscopic treatment , which was treated successfully, we have no febrile UTI post injection in our study, providing all patients was kept on suppressive antibiotic prophylaxis till the disappearance of VUR is proved by VCUG after 3 months post injection.

A recent meta-analysis of injection therapy considering outcomes from Dx/HA, polytetrafluoroethylene, collagen, polydimethylsiloxane, and chondrocytes suggested fewer subsequent UTIs than previously noted with open surgery or antibiotic prophylaxis, with an overall incidence of 6% (range 2.74%-14.15%) and febrile infection was observed in only 0.75% of the patients [27, 34].

Treatment failure in 9 ureters (13.6%), and planned for open reimplantation surgery.

Conclusion

The endoscopic treatment of VUR with Dx/HA is a feasible day case procedure, a minimally invasive method for VUR treatment in pediatric patients, requires minimal operating room time and causes low morbidity. Dx/HA is an effective substance in the endoscopic treatment of all grades of VUR.

This simple and minimally invasive treatment could be offered to all parents of children with VUR as an alternative to ureteral reimplantation because of high parents' preference.

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